

EFFECTIVE WAYS TO READ BOOKS**Rajabova Afruza Saloxiddinovna**Student of the Academic Lyceum of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of
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Annotation: the article highlights the benefits of reading, such as increasing communication, reducing stress, and boosting motivation. It also discusses common reading challenges and offer simple tips for improve focus. The article encourages readers to make reading a regular habit for personal growth.

Key words: reading books, issue, readers, students, skills, methods, benefits, information, motivation, meditation, timer.

In these days, it is not a secret that the world can be conquered through the science. So only way to gain a deep understanding of science is reading a book.

Nowadays, in our society great attention is paid to reading books. Young people`s interest in reading books is increasing day by day. We all know that reading books is really useful, because while we are reading we spiritual awakening and gain knowledge, interesting facts and information`s.

A.H.Baxmanyor once stated: "Look for a people whose a conversation feels like reading a book, and look for a book that feels like a conversation with philosopher." This quote has really deep meaning, which helps you become more successful in your life by avoiding unnecessary people and books.

Our state leader Shavkat Mirziyoyev expressed his opinion about reading books, including the following: "... nowadays there is an issue of great importance, namely to spread reading widely, we need to increase student`s intellectual immunity and raise their love to books to a higher level".

That is not secret, that a reader lives in two different worlds: the real world around us and the imaginative world within the book. Every book that I read feels like i am living on someone`s life, the worst part of it, it is finishing this life by not wanting it. It is really hard to describe the feeling that I got through while I read books. So, I want and wish reading books become everyone`s hobby, because it is not harmful, there are a lot of advantages of reading books.

Let me list top 4 benefits of reading books.

1) Empathy building

Well, books allow us to experience realities outside of our lives. They teach us to relate to others by often putting us in the shoe of the narrator. This simple technique is called empathy, it is defined as the ability to understand and share the feelings of another

2) Improving your conversation skills.

More we read, more we learn, more we know. So, when you read a lot you become a really good companion. Like you are ready to discuss any theme that your friend is talking about, because your circle of worldview is expanding. How? It is simple. You are reading, imagining it, getting and collecting really interesting facts and useful information. No one gets bored with a reader.

3) Decreasing stress

As I told that readers live in two worlds, so when you transport yourself to the another world you totally forget your problems, you are away from monotonous daily routine. By doing so, reading can decrease stress, lower heart rate and reduce blood pressure.

4) It motivates you.

As a person who get all motivation from the books I read, I can tell that it is for real. You see through your image how hard it is for the character in book, but despite of any challenges, he stays positive and never give up. By comparing your life with him, you will understand that you have to be more patient, spend time on the thing which could increase our knowledge.

Many of us make tiny mistakes by not noticing them while reading books. For example:

1) Articulation.

Articulation is reading aloud. Most of students' opinion reading out is really good method to catch the things easily, but unfortunately it is opposite. If you read aloud the steps will increase:

- 1- Step: your eyes will read
- 2- Step: you will read out with your mouth
- 3- Step: your ears will hear
- 4- Step: reaches the brain
- 5- Step: waste of your energy

Plus, to these, by reading out, you could interfere people near you. If you don't read aloud, steps will decrease.

- 1- Step: your eyes will read
- 2- Step: reaches the brain

2)“Regressive” reading

Regressive reading is reading backwards. Well, this type reading is happening when you were thinking about something while reading. Then to understand the context or meaning of that

paragraph, you reread that. After rereading firstly, you waste your time by coming back to that paragraph that you already read, secondly this book seems boring to you. The problem with this is, that you can't concentrate, let's say you reading and the main character is describing his birthday. And you immediately image your birthday party, by thinking how cool it was, full of fun, that your parents bought you a pink bicycle... you are reading but you are thinking out of theme, which worsen the situation.

As we came across to the problem with the concentration, to solve this issue, I will tell you a few ways to develop your focus while reading.

1) "The dot exercise"

This exercise is considered as one of the easiest and effective one. To do this exercise you need a paper and a pen. After getting them, you have to draw a point on the paper, then we have to sit on the chair and stick that piece of paper on the wall in front of you. Then you should look at that paper for 3 minutes, without any distractions. After a week of training, we have to increase it by 2 minutes. $3+2=5$. So for another week you train your focus for 5 minutes, 7 minutes, 9min, 11...

2) 5-4-3-2-1 technique

- 1) pay attention to five things you see around
- 2) choose something you can hold and see
- 3) pay attention to three sound you heard
- 4) feel two smells around you
- 5) find one thing that you can eat

Without any hesitation I can say that, this method helped me to develop my focus, because I was able to do this exercise whenever i want, wherever i want. It is convenient in anywhere. The main thing is to make it right.

3) Mindful meditation.

In modern psychotherapy meditation is used as an exercise to help you feel present and develop your concentration skills. To meditate, find a convenient place to do it. Close your eyes and silently observe your emotions, what are you feeling? What are experiencing. Do it every day for 5 minutes. If you want observe emotion more and stay calm, you can increase the time of meditation by 5 or even 10 minutes. Meditation makes a person feel better, it can reduce stress and anxiety, improve focus as I told and your mental health, reduce symptoms of depression.

Another effective way to focus is called "Listen to your interlocutor". This method more than just making a conscious effort to listen to your interlocutor's speech. Because it is important to spend time and mental effort to mentally process the information received. Then you start focusing on your companion's speech, by only analyzing it on your mind.

Orderly reading: In my opinion, every person should have time for reading, self-development. But, unfortunately a lot of people are not able to find time for reading. In the morning they have school (work), course, coming back they have to cook a dinner, clean, do homework... When you get some extra free time, you immediately scroll on your tiktok, watch your favorite show or film. But you can use this amount of time usefully. Let's say this amount of time equal to 1 hour. Now, I want to talk about “**Pomidor**” method. Which helps you maintain your time (1 hour).

How to use it?

1-step: you have to warn your parents that you will be busy for 1 hour, and tell them not to distract you.

2-step: then turn off all your gadgets, because they can interfere you from your task.

3-step: you need a timer and a book which you want read.

4-step: so set the timer for 25 minutes, and read, by living inner world of that book, work with your imagination.

5-step: after 25 minutes, set the timer for 5 minutes to relax. Relax doesn't mean scroll a tik-tok, or play games. It means to analyze all the information that you get from the context.

6-step: then you going to do the same thing, 25 minutes-reading, 5 minutes-to relax.

You can use this method to save your time, study effectively and not to be distracted easily.

In conclusion i can say that, you can really change your perspective on a world, by reading a lot of books. You will be a knowledgeable person, who knows a lot of information, facts, who is always ready to discuss any theme. To be this type of person, you have to use the tips that I gave and read books. It is really easy to get along with a book; you just need to open your heart to it.

References:

- 1) Mamatraimova H. “Bibliografiya”. O`zbekiston Milliy ensklopediyasi. A two-volume book. Teacher. 2001ю
- 2) Ahmadqulova A. “Kitob – hayotni yaratuvchi murabbiydir”. Yangi O`zbekiston gazetasi. Toshkent. 2021.